

Solvent Sublation for the Removal of a Hydrophobic Taste and Odour causing Organic from Aqueous Solution

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Manuscript received 4 February 1987, revised 5 February 1988, accepted 11 March 1988

Solvent sublation, an adsorptive bubble technique, was used to remove a taste and odour causing hydrophobic organic, viz. 2,3,6-trichloroanisole from aqueous solution. Considerable improvement over conventional fine bubble air stripping operations was observed. The effects of organic to aqueous phase volume ratio, the air flow rates, interferences from electrolytes upon the separation rate, and the effects of nonhydrophobic organics (e.g. ethanol, propanol) were studied.

THE need to remove low solubility organic contaminants from wastewaters and drinking water can never be over-emphasised on account of the deleterious effects they have on human health and the general environment. Apart from the fact that many of them are toxic and hence classified as priority pollutants by the U.S. EPA, some of them are cause for common complaints as taste and odour causing organics in municipal drinking water. Some compounds which fall in such a category are 2,3,6-trichloroanisole, 2-methylisoborneol and geosmin. Some of the methods which have been investigated for the removal of these compounds include activated carbon adsorption¹, resin adsorption², oxidation processes using chlorine, chlorine dioxide, ozone and potassium permanganate. A recent investigation by Pirbazari and coworkers³ focused upon the feasibility of air stripping as a removal method for taste and odour compounds. It was concluded that air stripping was, in general, not feasible mainly because of the very high air to water ratios required for acceptable removals. The reason for such a conclusion was the relatively low Henry's constants (and low vapor pressures) for these compounds. Air stripping (fine bubble aeration) depends solely on the favorable partitioning of the organic solute into the interior of the bubbles which are then released to the atmosphere as the bubbles break at the top of the aqueous section. Compounds of low Henry's constants (low vapor pressures) and low aqueous solubility are therefore difficult to strip from the aqueous phase. On the other hand, most of these compounds are hydrophobic and hence tend to aggregate (adsorb) at the air-water interface of the rising bubbles. Solvent sublation which is an 'adsorptive bubble technique' allows the removal of such compounds by levitating them on the air-water interface

of rising air bubbles and depositing them into a floating immiscible organic layer^{4,5}. Solvent sublation combines the effectiveness of both air stripping and solvent extraction to remove slightly volatile, non-volatile and volatile hydrophobics⁶. The solvent layer should be non-volatile, immiscible with water and should have a high affinity for the hydrophobic to be removed. It is conceivable that solvent sublation may reduce the extent of emission of volatile species to the atmosphere because of the solvent layer, though this is yet to be confirmed^{1,8}.

Wilson and coworkers have reported much success for solvent sublation in the removal of various hydrophobic pollutants from water⁶⁻¹⁰. Compounds that have been removed by solvent sublation include 1,1,1-trichloroethane, *o*- and *p*-dichlorobenzenes, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene, naphthalene, phenanthrene, aldrin, endrin, lindane, aromatic phthalate esters and pentachlorophenol. Valsaraj and Wilson^{7,11} reported a method for estimating the adsorption isotherm parameters for hydrophobics on the air-water interface of the rising bubbles and modeling the operation of batch and continuous solvent sublation processes. Detailed treatment of the various mathematical models were investigated by Valsaraj¹². In a recent review article Peters and coworkers¹⁵ indentified solvent sublation as an innovative mass transfer separation process for wastewater treatment. A summary of investigations on solvent sublation for wastewater reclamation was provided by Wilson and Pearson²⁵. Two of our recent papers give detailed accounts of the theory and applications of solvent sublation as an advanced wastewater treatment process^{20,20}.

The success of the process has been known to depend on certain important features: (1) the use of bubbles of very small size (preferably radii of

0.2 mm or less) so as to provide the maximum air-water interfacial area per unit volume and also to provide for a long residence time for the bubbles in the column (since smaller bubbles have slower rise velocities), and (ii) tall and narrow columns for longer bubble/water contact times and reduced axial dispersion for the bubbles in the column.

This paper focuses primarily on evaluating solvent sublation as a possible treatment alternative for taste and odour causing organics. We seek to establish that sublation is superior to conventional fine bubble aeration. 2,3,6-Trichloroanisole (TCA) is chosen as a representative compound since it is known to be the most potent known odour compound¹⁴. Since sublation is effective mainly for low solubility contaminants like TCA, the presence of other non-hydrophobics (like electrolytes) and more soluble organics (like alcohols) can severely interfere with this process. Such effects are also reported here as are the effects of air flow rates and phase volume ratios. The various effects reported here are of general applicability to those compounds amenable to removal by solvent sublation, viz. compounds with low aqueous solubility that are relatively non-volatile and of high hydrophobic character.

Experimental

The solvent sublation experiments were carried out in a pyrex glass column (100 cm × 5 cm o.d.). A porous silica sparger of fine porosity was fitted at the bottom of the column, which provided bubbles of average radii 0.2 mm in distilled water. Further details of the apparatus are given elsewhere^{6,13}. The initial aqueous volume was 1000 ml in most of the experiments. The solvent extraction studies were conducted in a 500 ml separatory funnel with 400 ml of the aqueous solution. Extraction equilibrium was achieved in a matter of few minutes.

2,3,6-Trichloroanisole (Aldrich) and mineral oil (Fisher Scientific, U.S.P. grade; mol. wt. 200, viscosity 56 cp) were used. Other chemicals used were ethanol, 1-propanol, 1-butanol, sodium sulphate, ammonium chloride and 1-octanol (all Fisher).

Saturated aqueous solutions of TCA were prepared by stirring of solid TCA in distilled water overnight, followed by filtration to remove any undissolved solids. Another method of preparing TCA solutions was by diluting with distilled water appropriate volumes of 10.25 g dm⁻³ of TCA dissolved in pure ethanol; these solutions had a mole fraction of 2 × 10⁻⁴ ethanol which helped reduce the bubble size (see Results and Discussion).

The analysis of TCA was accomplished using a Hewlett Packard 5890A gas chromatograph equipped with a nickel 63 electron capture detector. The carrier gas was 99.99% pre-purified nitrogen passed through a Alltech Associates gas purifier trap before reaching the column. A HP 530 μ series capillary

column (12 m × 0.2 mm i.d.) coated with crosslinked methyl silicone (OV-1) was used. The temperatures of the oven, detector and injector were 150, 300 and 250°, respectively. The total nitrogen flow was 20 ml min⁻¹ at 6 psi. Split injection with a split ratio 1 : 200 was used. Hamilton 701N 10 μl syringes were used for injection of samples. The peaks were stored and integrated on a HP 3392A computing integrator.

Runs were made as follows. The column was rinsed with distilled water, then filled with distilled water (1 dm³). The air flow rate was then adjusted to the desired value, the water drained off and then the column filled with the solution to be treated. On top of it was added the organic solvent (20–100 ml) and the timer started when the first sample was taken from the mid-port. At prescribed intervals, 4 ml samples were withdrawn from the mid-port and 1 ml pesticide grade hexane (Fisher) was added to it. The solutions were well shaken to ensure thorough extraction of TCA into hexane and stored in a Pierce Septum vial and refrigerated until analysis. After the run was complete the organic liquid was pipetted off and the solution drained from the bottom of the column. The column was rinsed, washed well with soap solution, then with acetone and repeatedly rinsed to remove all organic solvent. All experiments were conducted at 24 ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

2,3,6-Trichloroanisole (TCA) is a hydrophobic compound of low aqueous solubility and a Henry's constant of 28.8 × 10⁻⁵ atm m³ mol⁻¹ (Ref. 3). It has an estimated aqueous solubility of 31 mg dm⁻³, a vapor pressure of 0.03 mm/Hg and an octanol-water partition coefficient of 16000 (Ref. 26). TCA was chosen as the candidate for this study as it not only represents a taste and odour compound, but also serves as a prototype for other low solubility chlorinated hydrophobics of low Henry's constants and low vapor pressure; other examples being chlorinated pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls, etc.

Choice of solvent for sublation: As mentioned in the introduction, the choice of the organic solvent for sublation is of utmost importance as far as the success and utility of the process are concerned. The solvent should be non-volatile, immiscible with water and most of all should display a high affinity for the pollutant to be removed from the aqueous phase. This last criterion is of primary importance in solvent extraction also. Solvent sublation being a rate process (since the unidirectional upward motion of air bubbles account for the mass transfer) is said to be capable of achieving larger than the equilibrium removal normally attainable by solvent extraction. Moreover, in solvent sublation since the solvent phase is in minimal contact with the aqueous phase (as compared to the extraction process), the dissolution of

the organic solvent in the aqueous phase is also minimised. The advantage of sublation, therefore, lies in its ability to concentrate the pollutant in a very small volume of the solvent with minimal dissolution of the solvent in the aqueous phase. The contaminant-enriched solvent may be later destroyed by current methods such as incineration or mixing with boiler fuel¹⁶. Mineral oil or other petroleum-based hydrocarbons are recommended for these purposes. Hence, the experiments performed in this work as well as most of the reported work thus far^{7,8,12,18} have been on mineral oil as the solvent. It is also inexpensive and non-toxic. Another solvent which may be just as useful as mineral oil is fuel oil which is also incinerable after use; it is also immiscible with water, non-volatile and relatively inexpensive. A more common solvent for hydrophobic organics is 1-octanol, but it is not recommended for solvent sublation because of its fairly large aqueous solubility ($\sim 586 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$). This factor was explored in detail in the earlier work⁷. The extractive efficiency of mineral oil is displayed in Table 1. The usual dependence on the phase volume ratio is indicated. The mineral oil-water partition coefficient for TCA was estimated to be 730 ± 140 .

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF TCA MINERAL OIL,

Aqueous volume = 400 ml			
Mineral oil to aqueous volume ratio	Initial TCA concentration mg dm^{-3}	Final TCA concentration mg dm^{-3}	Percent extracted
1 : 100	4.6	1.6	65
1 : 40	4.6	0.4	91.9
1 : 20	5.1	0.12	97.6

Comparison of simple aeration and solvent sublation: Fig. 1 shows the effect of various volumes of mineral oil upon the solvent sublation of TCA. The improved performance of the sublation process as compared to air stripping without any mineral oil on top of the aqueous phase is apparent. This is due to the surface adsorbed TCA on the air bubble interface which is extracted into the mineral oil as the air bubbles transit the solvent phase. On the other hand, in conventional fine bubble aeration where there is no floating organic solvent, the adsorbed phase gets remixed with the aqueous phase as the bubbles break the surface of the aqueous phase and one gets removal of only the material carried within the interior of the air bubbles. Thus the air/water ratio required for appreciable removal of TCA from water is reduced considerably when solvent sublation is used instead of conventional bubble aeration. This is indeed the most important parameter which decides the economy of air stripping operations.

The effect of the phase volume ratio seems to be unimportant at solvent to aqueous volume ratios of 1 : 10 and 1 : 20. When the organic solvent volume is low (here ratios of 1 : 40 and 1 : 100) it

Fig. 1. The phase ratio effect on the solvent sublation of TCA. Organic/aqueous phase volume ratio = (●) aeration (no mineral oil used), (○) 1 : 100, (■) 1 : 40, (—) 1 : 20, and (▲) 1 : 10; mole fraction of ethanol = 2×10^{-4} .

has been reported^{7,8,12} that there is the possibility of considerable reverse mass transfer of solute from the solvent to the aqueous phase particularly because of the large turbulence set up at the solvent/aqueous interface as a result of the passage of air bubbles across the interface. This is further illustrated by the experiment involving the phase ratio of 1 : 100 in which 10 ml of mineral solvent was removed and replaced with the fresh. The extent of removal is apparently increased as a result. On a large scale, it may therefore be advantageous to use a slow continuous removal and replacement of the organic solvent. This dependence on solvent volume may also be explained by invoking a situation whereby only the upper enriched layers of the aqueous section are in equilibrium with the solvent layer and hence an extraction mechanism being operative. Models of solvent sublation proposed by Wilson and coworkers^{6,8} envisage such a situation where the aqueous section has an upper enriched layer and a depleted lower layer and therefore these concepts may profitably

be used to model the solvent volume dependence by incorporating the reverse mass transfer of the solute from the solvent layer to the upper layers of the aqueous section. At the low air flow rates generally used in sublation processes, the dissolution of mineral oil constituents in water does not seem to be a problem.

Effects of air flow rates on sublation : Increasing the flux of air through the column should increase the rate of removal from the aqueous phase. This effect is shown in Fig. 2. With the mode of bubble generation we used, i.e. using fritted discs, there is a limit to the bubble sizes that can be achieved (0.2 mm radius in this case) at low air flow rates.

Fig. 2. Effects of air flow rates upon the solvent sublation of TCA : (●) 0.65, (■) 1.2, and (○) 2.5 ml s⁻¹, phase volume ratio=1:40, mole fraction of ethanol = 2 × 10⁻⁴; C₀=8.5 mg dm⁻³.

But as the air flow rate increases, the population density of larger bubbles increases considerably in bubble columns¹⁷. The larger bubbles are detrimental to the sublation process for three important reasons. Firstly, larger bubbles provide reduced air-water interfacial area per unit volume of air (since this varies as 3/r, where r is the average

bubble radius). Secondly, larger bubbles have shorter residence times in the column (see Ref. 5 for details). These two effects combined will reduce the extent of mass transfer of solutes from the aqueous phase to the air bubbles. Thirdly, higher air flow rates also cause extensive axial dispersion within the column which has also been known to reduce the performance of the process⁸.

As shown in Fig. 2, the rate of removal does not seem to increase proportionally to the air flow rate at flow rates of 1.2 ml s⁻¹ and higher. The conclusion, therefore, is that increased flow rates would not be helpful unless there is a way to keep the effective bubble radius as small as possible. The use of other methods of bubble generation especially the so-called 'micro-gas dispersions'¹⁸ may be of considerable utility in this regard.

Since solvent sublation depends on the hydrophobic nature of solutes, it has been reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁰ that both electrolytes (e.g. NaCl, NaBr, Na₂SO₄) and non-electrolyte non-hydrophobics (e.g. methanol, ethanol, acetone) can influence the removal rates of hydrophobics by sublation. Understanding these effects are of tremendous importance if a large scale process on real wastes is contemplated. Following is a discussion of these effects.

Effects of electrolytes : The effects of electrolytes are presented in Figs. 3 and 4. The presence of electrolytes in the aqueous phase helps the sublation process in two important respects. Firstly, the presence of ionic species at the air-water interface of the air bubbles provide an energy barrier to bubble coalescence. This helps to maintain uniformly small bubble sizes in the column. Secondly, and more importantly, is the so-called 'salting-out' effect which decreases the solubility of the hydrophobic in aqueous solution. The above two factors together increases the separation rate^{8,10}. It is a well-known fact that the 'salting-out' effect increases with increasing ionic strength (electrolyte concentration). This effect is indicated in Fig. 3. The presence of different cations and anions are shown in Fig. 4. In general, it is evident that the effect varies as SO₄²⁻ > Cl⁻ > Br⁻ for anions and NH₄⁺ < Na⁺ for cations.

The effect of electrolytes upon the aqueous solubility of hydrophobics is best described by the McDevit-Long theory¹⁹ as described by Aquayun and coworkers²¹ which states that the solubility of a hydrophobic can be represented adequately by the empirical Setschenow equation¹⁹,

$$\log (\gamma/\gamma_0) = \log (S/S_0) = KC_s \quad (4)$$

where, γ , γ_0 are solute activity coefficients in water and electrolyte solutions, respectively, S , S_0 the solute solubilities in water and electrolyte solutions respectively, K the Setschenow constant, and C_s the molar concentration of the salt solution. The value of K depends upon the electrolyte and concentration. At low solute solubilities (as is the case

Fig. 3. Effects of various concentrations of sodium chloride upon the solvent sublation of TOA : NaCl=(●) 0.00, (○) 0.29, (▲) 0.51, (□) 0.99, and (Δ) 2.04 M, $C_0=3.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$ (no ethanol present, pure TOA dissolved in distilled water).

Fig. 4. Effects of different electrolytes upon the solvent sublation of TOA : (●) no electrolyte, (▲) 1 eq. NaBr, (○) 1 eq. NH_4Cl , (□) 1 eq. NaCl, and (Δ) 1 eq. Na_2SO_4 , air flow rate= 1.2 ml s^{-1} , phase ratio (O/W) = 1 : 40, $C_0=3.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$ (no ethanol present; pure TOA dissolved in distilled water).

here) K can be equated to the theoretical salt parameter, K_s which McDevit and Long²⁰ suggested can be given by the expression,

$$K_s = \frac{V_H(V_s - V_o)}{2.303 \beta RT} = V_H \xi \quad (5)$$

where, V_H is the partial molar volume of the hydrophobic in solution, V_o the partial molar volume of the salt in solution, V_s the molar volume of the liquid salt, β the compressibility of pure water, ξ a constant which depends only on the properties of salt and water.

The values of ξ for the different salts used in this study available in the literature²¹ are summarised in Table 2. It is evident from the tabulation of ξ and Fig. 4 that the order of variation in the 'salting-out' effect ($\text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-}$) and therefore the sublation rate are in satisfactory agreement with the McDevit-Long theory. It was noted that considerable foaming at the top of the mineral oil layer was prevalent in some of these

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ξ AND $(V_s - V_o)$ FOR VARIOUS ELECTROLYTES*

Electrolyte	ξ	$V_s - V_o$ (cm ³ /mol)
NaBr	0.00186	15.22
NaCl	0.00187	14.98
1/2 Na_2SO_4	0.00266	36.68

*Ref. 21.

experiments involving electrolytes, the problem being acute during the run with sodium bromide. It is believed that formation of water-in-oil emulsions is facilitated by the presence of salts in the aqueous phase.

Effects of non-electrolytes (non-hydrophobics): Non-hydrophobics have been reported¹⁰ to effect the sublation rate of hydrophobic compounds. The effects of ethanol of various concentrations are shown in Fig. 5. Two distinct effects are evident.

Fig. 5. Effects of various ethanol concentrations on the solvent sublation of TCA: X_{E+OH} = (●) 0.0, (■) 2×10^{-4} , (○) 2×10^{-3} , (▼) 2×10^{-2} and (Δ) 6×10^{-2} , air flow rate = 1.2 ml s^{-1} , phase ratio = 1 : 40, $C_0 = 3.5 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$ (pure TCA dissolved in distilled water).

Very low concentrations of ethanol (mole fractions of 2×10^{-4} and 2×10^{-3}) increase the sublation rate of TCA while large ethanol concentrations (2×10^{-2} and 6×10^{-2} mole fractions) decrease the sublation rate. Similar effects have been described by Wilson and coworkers¹⁰ and their explanation can be extended to our case as well.

The enhancement effect at low concentrations is attributable to two reasons. Firstly, it is a well-known observation that addition of ethanol decreases the surface tension of water²², and hence decreases the bubble size in our columns. This increases the air-water interfacial area per unit volume of air available for mass transfer and hence increases the rate of separation. Another well-established effect²³ is the stabilisation of hydrogen bonding of water up to ethanol mole fractions of 0.03. This makes the ethanol-water solution 'less comfortable' for the hydrophobic, which therefore prefers the air-water interface of the rising bubbles. This also increases the separation rate. However,

the effects of such low concentrations of ethanol on the solubility of hydrophobics are expected to be very small particularly in light of recent observations such as those of Herzl and Murty²⁴.

As the concentration of ethanol increases to 0.02 mole fraction and larger, another effect takes over, viz. the breaking of the hydrogen bonds in water and consequently the solubility of the hydrophobic molecule increases, thus decreasing its tendency to aggregate at the air-water interface of the air-bubbles. This effect (as regards sublation) is well documented¹⁰. This 'solubilising effect' can be better characterised using the two-suffix Margule's equation²⁴ as described by Mackay and coworkers²⁷. The ratio of solubility (S) of the hydrophobic in the presence of a co-solute to that in pure water is then given by

$$\log S = X_3(A_{12} - A_{13} + A_{23}) = X_3A$$

where, A represents 'interaction parameters', X the mole fraction, 1 refers to the hydrophobic, 2 refers to water and 3 refers to the organic co-solute.

The significant conclusions from the above equation are summarised below.

(i) The greatest solubilising effect will be shown by co-solute which tends to increase S rapidly as X_3 increases which occurs when A_{13} is very small, i.e. the co-solute has organic character similar to those of the hydrophobic solute and thus compatible with it.

(ii) The same effect is possible when A_{23} is very large, i.e. when there is relatively high non-ideality between co-solute and water. It should then be expected that higher molecular weight compounds will be more effective solubilisers than are low molecular weight ones. This effect is displayed in Fig. 6 which shows that 1-propanol is a better solubiliser for TCA than ethanol, and hence decreased the rate of sublation more than does ethanol. This is in agreement with reported results¹⁰ on the sublation of aldrin (a chlorinated pesticide) that the longer the chain length of the alcohol the more effective it is in reducing the removal rate. It is also conceivable that long chain alcohols which form self-aggregate assemblies, i.e. micelles, can trap the hydrophobic molecules (like TCA) within their hydrocarbon like cores. These micellar entities are not amenable to adsorption at air-water interfaces and hence are non-floatable. Therefore, it can be deduced that high concentrations of alcohols would, in any event, be detrimental to the sublation process.

It should be noted that the experiments reported here are at concentrations of TCA greater than its odour threshold, viz. nanograms per liter range. At these concentrations TCA analysis becomes extremely difficult, although methods like closed loop stripping analysis⁸ are available. In view of what is reported in this paper, it is recommended that sublation be carried out at the lower concentration ranges to determine its feasibility at these concentration ranges.

Fig. 6. Effects of ethanol and propanol on the solvent sublation of TCA : (○) 2×10^{-3} ethanol and (●) 2×10^{-3} propanol, phase volume ratio=1: 40, air flow rate = 1.2 ml s^{-1} .

On the basis of these results it is anticipated that similar degrees of effectiveness of removal by sublation may be observed for other taste and odour organics of similar properties viz. low aqueous solubility, low vapor pressure (low Henry's constant) and high hydrophobic character.

However, we would like to close this section with the caution that the use of solvent sublation for large scale municipal waste water treatment may entail certain problems especially in light of scanty pilot plant results that are presently available²⁵. For example, the relatively high solids content of municipal wastewater may help being some solvent into the aqueous section while the presence of any 'immiscible' solvent in drinking water is highly undesirable. Bubble coalescence may also be a problem when high solids strength is present in the wastewater. Moreover, the bacterial lifeforms present in municipal wastewater may help to biodegrade the solvent layer and thereby reduce its effectiveness. Thus it appears that relatively low solids strength and low bacterial content are

essential for the success of solvent sublation for large scale municipal wastewater treatment process. In industrial wastewater treatment where a residual of organic solvent could be tolerated, solvent sublation may be more useful. Our lab-scale experiments including this paper and others^{7,8,12,29,30} indicate that solvent sublation merits consideration as an advanced wastewater treatment process for non-polar (slightly polar), low solubility hydrophobics. More recently we have reported on the solvent sublation of such a hydrophobic (pentachlorophenol) from an actual waste water sample from a wood preserving industry³⁰. More results of such experiments are summarised in an upcoming review³¹.

Acknowledgement

This research was conducted while the senior author was at the Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Arkansas. One of the authors (K.T.V.) wishes to thank Dr. James L. Gaddy, Chairman of the Department of Chemical Engineering for financial support. The experimental assistance of Ms. Janet Menshek is gratefully acknowledged.

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